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Research Article

**SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND INVITRO
EVALUATION OF 4,6-DIPHENYL PYRIMIDINE-2(1H)-
THIONE DERIVATIVES.****K. Durga Lalitha Rani, A. Teja, V. Mythili, V. Naveen Kumar, D. Kiranmayee,
Sudha Rani. K*.**Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Sri Siddhartha Pharmacy College,
Ammavarithota, Nuzvid.**Abstract:**

A Series of Bioactive compounds , 4,6-diphenyl Pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione(1a), 4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine-2-(1H)-thione(1b),4-(4-aminophenyl)-6-phenyl pyrimidine -2(1H) thione (2a) , 4-(4-nitro phenyl)-6-phenyl pyrimidine-2(1H)- thione (2b) , 4-(4- methoxy phenyl)-6-phenyl pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione(3a), were synthesized according to the literature methods . The synthesized compounds were characterized by NMR, IR & Mass spectroscopy. All the compounds have been evaluated for invitro anti-bacterial activity, anti-fungal activity, anti-helminthic activity and were compared with their corresponding standards.

Keywords: 4,6-diphenyl pyrimidine-2(1H)-Thione, Chalcones, Aldehydes, Thiourea, Ciprofloxacin, Fluconazole, Albendazole.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Synthetic derivatives demonstrate an essential role in modern medicines such as quinazoline alkaloids, which Exhibit hypnotic activity ^[1]. Many simple fused pyrimidines such as purines and pteridine are biologically active. Some Have bronchodilator potential and act as antagonist of the human A2A adenosine receptor and constitute some Valuable naturally occurring substances such as nucleic acids.^[2] Similarly, the presence of a pyrimidine base in cytosine, Uracil, and thymine (building blocks of DNA and RNA) is one of the possible reasons for their activities. Some Pteridine derivatives are also used as antileukemic drugs ^[3]. moreover, a pyrimidine ring is also found in isalloxazine Vitamin B2 flucytosine (used as a nucleoside antifungal agent for the treatment of systemic severe infections), Thiamine, riboflavin(6,7-dimethyl-9(D-1-ribityl), and folic acid ^[4]. A few pyrimidine derivatives also show Potassium-conserving diuretic and anti-malarial activity ^[5]. The biological significance of the pyrimidine derivatives has led us to the synthesis of substituted pyrimidine. As pyrimidine is a basic nucleus in DNA & RNA, it has been found to be associated with diverse biological Activates^[6].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Melting points were determined in open glass capillaries using Gallen Kamp (MFB- 600) melting point apparatus and were uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr discs) Bruker analysers were confirmed by Shimadzu FTIR Spectrophotometer using KBr pellets technique, Model No.8400S (Japan). ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 400 MHz NMR spectrometer (Switzerland) using DMSO as solvent. T.L.C. was run on silica gel G plates using ethyl acetate: n-hexane (7:3) as developing solvent to assess the progress of reaction and purity of the compounds. All other chemicals used in the present study were of analytical grade.

2.1 Drugs and chemicals:

Benzaldehyde- (FINAR.B.NO.60107022LU),Chlorobenzaldehyde(PALLAV.B.NO.PC/388-L/17-L),Nitrobenzaldehyde(PALLAV.B.NO.PC/2186/16-L),Acetophenone (FINAR.B.NO.50560212BP), Ethano (CCS.B.NO.110605), KOH(www.researchlab.in.1245190918),Thiourea(universallaboratories. B.NO. C123811169), Ethyl acetate (AVRA), Silica gel-G- (RESEARCH-LAB FINE CHEM industries- B.NO.I317310113),Anisaldehyde(ULTRAPURE-LABCHEMINDUSTRIES.B. NO.AA/277/21), Aminobenzaldehyde (SIGMA-ALDRICH, Co., 3050Sprucest.), n-Hexane (PHARMACO-AAPER.B.NO. WO115400).

3. Chemical synthesis:

Step-1: Synthesis of substituted chalcone derivatives:

Equimoles of different benzaldehydes and acetophenones were taken into mortar, and pulverized by pestle at room temperature by employing the friction method. Then the mixture was moist with few drops of ethanol and KOH. The progress of the reaction was checked by TLC, and all the reactions were found to be completed in times of 10-12 min. The product was recrystallized from ethanol. The purity was confirmed by thin-layer chromatography and melting point.

Step-2: Synthesis of Pyrimidine compounds:

Equimoles of substituted chalcone derivatives and thiourea were taken into mortar, and pulverized by pestle at room temperature by employing the friction method at room temperature using ethanol, KOH. The mixture was neutralized and transferred to ice cold water, precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. The purity and progress of reaction was confirmed by thin layer chromatography.

SCHEME:

Step-1:

Step-2:

Where R: Cl, NH₂, NO₂, OCH₃

TABLE 1: PHYSICAL DATA:

Code	Compound	M.F	M.W	%yield	C%	H%	O%	N%	Cl%	S%
1a	4,6-diphenyl pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	264.34	72%	72.70	4.58	–	10.60	–	12.13
1b	4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-phenyl pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ S	298.07	74%	64.32	3.71	–	9.38	11.87	10.73
2a	4-(4-amino phenyl)-6-phenyl pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	279.36	75%	68.79	4.69	–	15.04	–	11.48
2b	4-(4-nitro phenyl)-6-phenyl pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	309.34	78%	62.12	3.58	10.34	13.58	–	10.37
3a	4-(4-Methoxy phenyl)-6-phenyl pyrimidine-2(1H)-thione	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	294.37	78%	69.36	4.79	5.44	9.52	–	10.89

Compound [1a]: Synthesis of 4,6-diphenyl 2(1H)-thione: Yield-72%; **IR Data:** FTIR (γ max, C m-1) 1650 (-C=C), 2050 (=C-H stretch), 1500 (=C-H bend), 1590 (-C=N), 3000 (- C-NH), 1150 (C-N-), 1250 (C=S), 2500 (C-SH). **¹HNMR:** (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 6.6, 6.8, 7.0, 7.1, 7.2, 7.21, 7.38, 7.45, 7.7, 8.1, 8.2 (Ar-H). **¹³CNMR:** (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 120.3, 120.7, 121.1, 122.3, 130.5, 130.9, 135.6, 141.4, 145.8, 146.6, (C-H), δ 152.34 (C=N), δ 190.6 (C=S).

Compound [1b]: Synthesis of 4-(4-chlorophenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine-2(1H)- thione:

Yield- 74%, **IR Data:** FTIR (γ max, C m-1) 1640(-C=C), 2842(= C-H stretch), 1510(=C-H bend), 1145 (-C-N), 2990(-C-NH), 2510(SH), 1255(C=S), 710(-C CL), -1600(C=N). **¹HNMR:** (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 6.1, 6.5, 7.4, 7.5, 7.9, 8.05, 8.1, 8.19, 8.26, 8.34, (Ar-H). **¹³CNMR:** (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 120.1, 120.9, 121.3, 122.5, 123.3, 134.4, 136.9, 141.2, 145.6, 145.7 (C-H), δ 153.24 (C=N), δ 55.9 (C=Cl), δ 190.1 (C=S).

Compound [2a]: Synthesis of 4-(4-aminophenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine-2(1H)-thione:

Yield- 75%, **IR Data :** FTIR (γ max, C m-1) 1660(-C=C stretch), 2855(= C-H stretch), 1505 (=C-H bend), 1155 (-C-N), 3010 (- C-NH). 1260(C=S), 2505(C-SH), 3010(C-NH). 3300(C-NH₂). **¹HNMR :** (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 6.12, 6.24, 6.7, 7.31, 7.42, 7.41, 7.53, 7.59, 7.6, 7.89, (Ar-H). **¹³CNMR:** (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 120.0, 123.1, 123.5, 133.5, 135.5, 145.3, 145.7, 148.0, 149.5, 150.0 (C-H), δ 151.34 (C=N), δ 190.1 (C=S), δ 129.08 (C-NH₂).

Compound [2b]: Synthesis of 4-(4-nitrophenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine-2(1H)-thione: Yield- 78%, **IR Data:**

FTIR (γ max, C m-1) 1655(-C=C stretch), 2860 (= C-H stretch), 1515 (=C-H bend), 1610 (-C=N), 3005 (- C-NH). 1268(C=S), 2525(C-SH), 3005(C-NH), 1470(C-NO₂). **¹HNMR:** (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 6.31, 6.35, 6.7, 6.81, 6.85, 7.12, 7.4, 7.54, 7.85, 7.91, (Ar-H). **¹³CNMR:** (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 128.9, 130.1, 132.2, 135.5, 135.6, 136.2,

136.9, 137.1, 145.5, 146.4 (C-H), δ 154.34 (C=N), δ 190.3 (C=S), δ 146.1 (C-NO₂).

Compound [3a]: Synthesis of 4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine-2(1H)-thione: Yield 78%, **IR Data:** FTIR (γ max, C m⁻¹) 1645(-C=C stretch), 2865(= C-H stretch), 1525 (=C-H bend), 1142 (C-N), 3015 (- C-NH).1258(C=S), 2515(C-SH),3015(C-NH),1605 (C=N).

¹H NMR (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 6.4, 6.45, 6.78, 6.9, 7.01, 7.57, 7.89, 8.02, 8.23, 8.34, (Ar-H).

¹³C NMR: (500MHZ, CDC13), δ 121.5, 123.6, 125.01, 130.4, 135.5, 145.5, 146.6, 147.1,148.5, 150.0 (C-H), δ 151.34 (C=N), δ 79.9 (C-OCH₃), δ 190.9 (C=S).

1. EXPERIMENTAL WORK:

ANTI-BACTERIAL ACTIVITY [7] :

Experimental Procedure:

All the synthesized compounds were examined for invitro antibacterial activity against an assortment of two gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* NCIM 2901 and *Bacillus subtilis* MTCC 441 and

gram negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by diffusion method. Ciprofloxacin were used as an internal standard.

Nutrient agar(Hi-media) was dissolved and distributed in 25 ml quantities in boiling tubes and were sterilised in an autoclave at 121°C (15Lbs/sq.in) for 20 minutes. The medium was inoculated at one percent level using 18 hours old cultures of the test organism mentioned above aseptically into sterile petridishes and allowed to set at room temperature for about 30 minutes. In a size of 4 inches petridishes, five cups of 8mm diameter at equal distance were made in each plate. In the cups the test solutions of different concentration were added and in another plate cups were made for standard and control. The plates thus prepared were left for 90 minutes in a refrigerator for diffusion. After incubation for 16 hours at 37°C the plates were examined for inhibition zones. The experimental was performed in duplicate and the average diameter of the zones of inhibition measured is recorded. The results were represented in table 2.

Table-2: Anti-bacterial Activity :

Zone of inhibition (Diameter in Cm)															
Compound	Bacillus subtilis					Staphylococcus aureus					Pseudomonas aeruginosa				
	50 μ /ml	100 μ /ml	150 μ /ml	200 μ /ml	250 μ /ml	50 μ /ml	100 μ /ml	150 μ /ml	200 μ /ml	250 μ /ml	50 μ /ml	100 μ /ml	150 μ /ml	200 μ /ml	250 μ /ml
1a	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.7	1.9
1b	1.1	1.3	1.3	1.5	1.6	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6
2a	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.4	1.5	1.4	1.7	1.8
2b	0.9	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5
3a	1	1.1	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.8	1.3	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8
Standard (ciprofloxacin)	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7

Fig 1: Anti Bacterial Activity**ANTI-FUNGAL ACTIVITY [8] :**

The antifungal activity of compound were assayed against three different strains of *Aspergillus Niger* MTCC 282, *pencillium chrysogenum* MTCC 5108 and *pencillium notatum* NCIM 742. Potato dextrose agar (Hi- media) was dissolved and distribution in 25ml quantities in 100ml conical flask and were sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C (151bs/sq.in) for 20 minutes. The medium was inoculated at one percent level using 18hr old cultures of organisms mentioned above aseptically in to sterile petridish 5 cups of 8mm diameter at equal distance were made in

petri plate with a sterile borer.

The solutions of test and standard at concentrations (250µg/ml, 200µg/ml, 150 µg/ml, 100 µg/ml, and 50 µg/ml) were added to respective cup aseptically and labelled accordingly. DMF as control did not show any inhibition.

The plates were left for 90 minutes in refrigerator for diffusion. After incubation for 24 hrs at 37° 1⁰ c.

The plates were examined for incubation inhibition zones. The experiments were performed in duplicate and the average diameters of the zones of inhibition were summarized in table 3.

Table-3: Anti-fungal Activity:

Zone of inhibition (Diameter In Cm)															
Compound	Aspergillus Niger					Pencillium chrysogenum					Pencillium notatum				
	50µ/ml	100 µ/ml	150 µ/ml	200 µ/ml	250 µ/ml	50 µ/ml	100 µ/ml	150 µ/ml	200 µ/ml	250 µ/ml	50µ/ml	100 µ/ml	150 µ/ml	200 µ/ml	250 µ/ml
1a	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.7
1b	1	1.2	1.3	1.5	1.6	1	1.1	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
2a	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5
2b	0.8	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.3	1	1.1	1.2	1.5	1.5
3a	1.1	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.7	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6
Standard (Fluconazole)	0.9	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6

Fig 2 : Anti Fungal Activity

ANTI-HELMINTIC ACTIVITY [9] :

Indian adult earthworms of the genus and species, *Pheritima posthuma* (family: Megascolecidae), were used to study the antihelmintic activity. The earthworms were collected from the water logged areas of soils in Vijayawada, Andhra Pradesh, India were washed with normal saline to remove all the faecal matter and waste surrounding their body. The earth worms (*Pheritima posthuma*) 5-8 cm in length and 0.2-0.3 cm width weighing 0.8- 3.04 g were used for all experiment protocols. The earthworms resembled the intestinal roundworm parasites of human beings both anatomically and physiologically and hence were used to study the antihelmintic activity.

Procedure:

1% Gum acacia solution prepared in normal saline, different concentrations was prepared by using this solution.

Sample were taken petriplates and adult healthy earth worms (n=6) were introduced in to them. Observations were made for the time taken to paralyze and time taken for death of the organism. Paralysis was said to occur when the worms do not review even in normal saline. Death was concluded when worms lost their motility followed by fading away of the body colour.

Table.4: Anti-helmintic activity:

Sl.No	Compounds	Dose	Paralysis time in minutes	Death time in minutes
			Mean±s.e.m	Mean±s.e.m
1	Control (Normal saline)	100mg/ml	-----	-----
2	1a	100mg/ml	109.2±21.1	247.6±6.17
3	2a	100mg/ml	119.6±9.35	220.2±4.58
4	1b	100mg/ml	128±11.06	232±4.06
5	2b	100mg/ml	88.6±6.8	211.8±6.06
6	3a	100mg/ml	69.8±2.59	200.2±3.33
7	Albendazole	100mg/ml	24.4±4.54	88.6±9.61

Fig 3 : Anti Helmintic Activity**Figure-3.3 : Saline solution**

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The compounds were tested for anti-bacterial and anti-fungal activity against an assortment of two gram- positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* NCIM 2901, *Bacillus subtilis* MTCC 441, one gram-negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and three fungal strains *Aspergillus Niger* MTCC 282 *Pencillium chrysogenum* MTCC \$108 and *Pencillium notatum* NCIM 742. Ciprofloxacin were used as standards to assess anti-bacterial activity and Fluconazole was used as standard to assess anti-fungal activity The results of antimicrobial study of synthesized compounds were shown in **table 2 and table 3**. All the compounds showed significant anti-microbial activity Of all the derivatives synthesized compound **1a,2a,3a** exhibited good and compound **1b,2b** showed moderate anti-microbial properties.

Physicochemical and analytical data were tabulated for synthesized compounds as shown in Table 1. The Structures of the compounds were characterised through IR and IH and ¹³C NMR Spectral data, whereas results of anti-helminthic studies tabulated in Table 4 reveals that compound 3a,2b,2a was found to be the most potent Compound inthe series which when compared to the standard, compounds **3a,2b,2a** showed high activity, other compounds **1a,1b** showed significant anti-helminthic activity.

3. CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, we have developed a simple, benign and expeditious synthesis of biologically significant pyrimidine derivatives with good yields under mortar and pestle grinding method and fully characterized the products by IR, ¹H NMR, Mass spectral and Elemental analysis. The Synthesis of Pyrimidine derivatives by mortar and pestle grinding The findings of the study inferred the design and that the functioning of synthesized compounds as anti-helminthic agents, anti-microbial agents and anti-fungal agents rendering them as lead molecules for further development of newer with greater efficacy and safety.

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